

Countering COVID-19: A European survey on acceptability of and commitment to preventive measures

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: European countries undertook a range of countermeasures to contain and mitigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, including international and domestic mobility restrictions, school closures, bans of public gatherings, and lockdowns. Some countries have been considering the implementation of more controversial interventions, such as banning medical exports or usage of mobile phone data for tracking purposes.

This study aimed at investigating the public sentiment towards the containment measures undertaken in Europe at the onset of the COVID-19 outbreak to learn about people's support for containment policies, their worries in relation to the unfolding epidemic, and their trust in different sources of information.

In order to understand the public sentiment towards the COVID-19 containment measures and to inform future policy development, we collected information on people's support for these policies, their worries in relation to the unfolding epidemic, and their trust in different sources of information.

Methods: We surveyed over 7,000 people representative of the adult population in seven European countries: Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Portugal, the Netherlands, and the UK. The fieldwork was conducted online during April 2-15, 2020, using multi-sourced online panels provided by the market research company Dynata.

To ensure that the sampling frame was representative given the online nature of the study, the company applied diverse recruiting procedures to reach the general population (through open recruitment, loyalty programs, affiliate networks, mobile apps). It then used quotas to match the national census shares in each country. The questionnaire was designed by the authors of the study except for the worry items that were adopted from the World Health Organization (WHO) COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring project.

The questionnaire was carefully translated into six other languages by native speakers and then implemented using the Qualtrics platform first as a pilot (10% of the sample in every country) and next as a large-scale survey. The data from the pilot study were included in the total sample. In each country, we collected data from a sample of 1,000 respondents representative of the national population in terms of region, age, gender, and education. Given that the Italian region Lombardy was the most severely hit by the COVID-19 outbreak, we collected 500 additional responses in this region representative in terms of age and gender. Learning about perceptions and attitudes of people who reside there could provide essential insights to researchers and policymakers. The extra data collected from Lombardy were not included in the representative sample of Italy. Thus, no weighting was used as the additional Lombardy sample was analyzed separately.

Key Findings:

- Citizens were overall satisfied with their government's response to the COVID-19 outbreak
- A north-south pattern in public opinion, worry and trust was observed across the European states

- Pandemic acted as a stressor, causing health and economic anxieties even in households that were not directly impacted by COVID-19
- Considerable differences in levels of trust were observed between and within countries
- Containment policies offered lessons for the design of lockdown exit strategies